

ANDIJAN CITY PUBLIC TRANSPORT TO PROVIDE PRIORITY OF MOVEMENT

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Abstract: This article reveals the set of actions that should be taken to ensure the priority of public transport in the city of Andijan.

Keywords words and phrases: public transport, priority, passenger, bus, bus lanes Bus rapid transit BRT, optimal means of transport, peregon, station, sidewalks, road - infrastructure object facilities, modern standard.

In recent years, large-scale work has been carried out to improve the provision of motor transport services to the population, expand the network of public transport routes and update the traffic structure with modern, environmentally friendly buses. Today, scientific and practical work is being carried out on the development of public transport throughout our Republic, ensuring its priority, providing high-quality, cheap and affordable transport services to the population. Today's goal is not only to deliver passengers to their destinations, but public transport is distinguished by the fact that it provides safe and fast service to passengers that improves the ecological environment of the city. At the same time, bus lanes with special markings and bus rapid transit (Bus rapid transit BRT) lanes have been established in developed countries to ensure the priority of public transport traffic.

Figure 1. Bus rapid transit network (Japan)

The clear purpose of bus lanes today is not only to get passengers to their destinations, but also to be more convenient than using a taxi service without directions or a private vehicle. Such actions will lead to the elimination of the

problem of traffic jams, increasing the level of use of public transport by the representatives of the population rather than private transport or other optimal means of transport.

Of course, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 16, 2023 "On measures to reform the public transport system" No.

In Annex 3 of this decision, the "Road Map" for improving the public transport system in the city of Andijan was developed. According to the 11th point of the road map "Development of road transport infrastructure in order to ensure the priority of public transport" in the years 2023-2025, it is planned to introduce separate bus lanes on the streets where public transport is constantly moving in the city of Andijan. Based on this, during 2023-2025, a total of 36.4 km long separate bus lanes are set to be established.

Figure 2. Separate bus lane project

Figure 3. Babur Avenue (regulated intersections)

As a result of studies, first of all, the following problems exist in these streets:

- presence of unregulated sidewalks;
- presence of unregulated intersections;
- the fact that the number of lanes on some highways is 4 (the width of the road is not based on standards);
- it was found that the location of some bus stops is far from populated areas and the location is not based on standards.

Of course, it is recommended that the optimal distance between stops on city bus routes is from 300 to 700 meters, depending on the length of the passenger journey. Taking into account the distance between platforms in Andijan, the areas where bus stops are located show that it is necessary to reconsider. The longer the distance between the peregons, the higher the average technical speed of public transport. (Peregon is the distance between two adjacent stops of passenger transport)

Based on this, the city of Andijan orders the revision of road infrastructure facilities based on modern standards.

This article can be used by master's degree specialists and intern researchers, independent researchers, and professors who deal with the problems of scientific research and creativity in all higher education institutions.

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